

Some β -Phenethylamine Derivatives. Part III

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Several substituted β -phenethylamines have been synthesised by the lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the corresponding β -nitrostyrenes, the latter being obtained from the appropriate aldehydes.

The present communication is a continuation of our previous work¹ and describes synthesis of several substituted β -phenethylamines obtained by the lithium aluminium hydride² reduction of β -nitrostyrene derivatives, the latter being prepared from the appropriate aldehydes by condensation with nitromethane in acetic acid medium in presence of ammonium acetate³.

The aldehydes listed in Table I (No. 1 to 9) are hitherto unknown. Aldehyde (3) was prepared by the Gattermann reaction on 2-benzylresorcinol, the latter being obtained by the Clemmensen reduction of 2-benzoylresorcinol.

Aldehyde (7) was prepared by the Gattermann reaction on 2,3,5-trimethylphenol. Its m.p. differed from the known isomeric 6-hydroxy-2,4,5-trimethylbenzaldehyde; also it did not exhibit ferric chloride coloration, confirming its structure as compound (7).

The remaining aldehydes were prepared by alkylation of the corresponding hydroxybenzaldehydes with methyl or ethyl iodide in acetone solution in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. The various β -phenethylamines and the β -nitrostyrenes are described in Table II. Wherever the latter were obtained as oils, these were subjected to reduction without further purification. The amines were isolated as their picrates.

TABLE I

No.	Benzaldehydes.	2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.				
		Aldehydes.	2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.		% Nitrogen.	
		M.P.	Formula.	M.P.	Found	Reqd.
1	2,4-Dimethoxy-3-methyl-	49°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₄	215°	15.20	15.55
2	2,4-Diethoxy-3-methyl-	Oil	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₄	186°	14.20	14.48
3	3-Benzyl-2,4-dihydroxy-	136°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₄	272°	12.90	13.72
4	3-Benzyl-2,4-dimethoxy-	Oil	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₄	192°	12.60	12.84
5	3-Benzyl-2,4-diethoxy-	..	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₄	176°	12.40	12.30
6	2-Methoxy-4,5-dimethyl-	68°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄	269°	16.50	16.27
7	4-Hydroxy-2,3,6-trimethyl-	135°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄	234°	16.00	16.27
8	4-Methoxy-2,3,6-trimethyl-	50°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₄	197°	15.90	15.60
9	2-Methoxy-3,5-dimethyl-	Oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄	227°	16.60	16.27

1. Merchant and Khan, this *Journal*, 1962, **39**, 227.

2. Erze and Ramirez, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1950, **23**, 912; Ramirez and Burger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1950, **72**, 2782.

3. Gairud and Lappin, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 1.

TABLE II

No.	Benzaldehydes.	β -Nitrostyrenes.			β -Phenethylamines.				
		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen Found. Reqd.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen Found. Reqd.		
1	2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxy-	132°	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ N	5.90	5.90	195°	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₄	13.00	12.80
2	4,5-Dimethoxy-2-methyl-	155°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	6.40	6.27	180°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₄	13.60	13.23
3	3-Ethyl-2,4-dimethoxy-	109°	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ N	5.60	5.90	170°	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₄	12.60	12.80
4	2,4-Dimethoxy-3-methyl-	104°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	6.50	6.27	20°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₄	13.10	13.23
5	2,4-Diethoxy-3-methyl-	87°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	6.00	5.60	181°	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₄	12.60	12.38
6	3-Benzyl-2,4-dimethoxy-	110°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	5.10	4.70	176°	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₄	11.60	11.20
7	3-Benzyl-2,4-diethoxy-	Oil	..	..	..	168°	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₄	10.80	10.60
8	2-Methoxy-4,5-dimethyl-	107°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	7.10	6.80	310°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄	13.80	13.70
9	4-Methoxy-2,3,6-trimethyl-	Oil	..	..	..	184°	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄	13.60	13.30
10	2-Methoxy-3,6-dimethyl-	..	..	..	..	163°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄	14.10	13.70
11	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-	181°	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂	14.90	14.58	170°	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₁₄ N ₈ *	18.30	18.00
12	3,4-Dibenzoyloxy-	130°	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	4.00	3.87	117°	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₄	10.20	10.00
13	3-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-	134°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	6.50	6.27	166°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₄	13.60	13.23

*Dipicrate.

EXPERIMENTAL

β -Nitrostyrene.—A mixture of the aldehyde (5 g.), nitromethane (5 ml), ammonium acetate (2 g.), and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed at 130° for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid separating was crystallised from methanol or acetic acid. If no solid separated, the resulting solution was poured into ice-water and the pasty material obtained was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried, and the solvent distilled when either a solid or an oil was left behind. The solid was purified by crystallisation, whereas the oil was directly subjected to reduction.

β -Phenethylamine.—Reduction of the β -nitrostyrene with LiAlH₄ to the corresponding β -phenethylamine was carried out according to the general method followed by Erno and Ramirez⁵.

A solution of the β -nitrostyrene (3 g.) in dry ether (30 ml) was added dropwise to a well-stirred suspension of LiAlH₄ (2 g.) in dry ether (10 ml). A mixture of ether and benzene was employed for the styrenes which were sparingly soluble in ether. The reaction mixture was refluxed gently for 5 hours and then decomposed with ice-cold water (180 ml). The reaction mixture was filtered and the ethereal layer was separated from the aqueous layer. Removal of the ether left an oily residue which was dissolved in absolute ethanol and added to a hot ethanolic solution of picric acid. On cooling, yellow or orange crystals of the amine picrate were obtained which crystallised from ethanol or a mixture of ethyl acetate and light petroleum; yield about 60%.

Alkylation of Hydroxybenzaldehydes.—A mixture of aldehyde (5 g.), potassium carbonate (anhyd., 10 g.), methyl or ethyl iodide (5 ml), and dry acetone (100 ml) was refluxed for about 20 hours. Filtration and removal of acetone provided an oil which was taken up in ether and washed successively with 2% NaOH solution and water. Removal of the solvent yielded the alkylated aldehyde as a low-melting solid or an oil; yield 80-85%.

3-Benzyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde.—Zinc cyanide (28 g.) was added to a solution of 2-benzylresorcinol (20 g.) in dry ether (250 ml). The mixture was stirred vigorously

and dry HCl gas passed rapidly into the mixture till saturation (≈ 4 hours). The ether was then decanted from the solid product and water (300 ml) added to the solid. The solid residue was then boiled with water and sufficient ethanol was added to the hot aqueous solution to bring about complete solution. On cooling, a crystalline compound, m. p. 136-38°, was obtained; yield 13 g.

4-Hydroxy-2,3,5-trimethylbenzaldehyde.—To a mixture of 4-hydroxy-2,3,5-trimethylphenol (20 g.), zinc cyanide (40 g.), and dry benzene (200 ml), taken in a three-necked flask fitted with a mercury sealed stirrer and a reflux condenser, cooled in an ice bath, was passed dry HCl gas for 30 minutes. Powdered aluminium chloride (30 g.) was then added and the passage of HCl was continued. After 30 minutes the temperature was raised to 40° which was maintained for 6 to 7 hours, stirring and passage of HCl being continued all the while. Next day, the benzene was decanted and the product washed with benzene. It was then added to 200 ml of ice-cold water. Sufficient ethanol was then added to the hot aqueous solution to bring about complete solution. On cooling, a solid separated. After crystallisation from dilute alcohol it had m. p. 136°; yield 14 g.

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